

THE GOALS OF EDUCATION AS THE GOALS OF HUMAN LIFE

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Abstract

The appeal to the problem of identifying the goals of human education is due to the discrepancy between the level of conscious independence of school and university graduates achieved today and the goals of a full-fledged (personal and social) human life. One of the reasons for this discrepancy is, on the one hand, the reduction in hours devoted to studying philosophy in Russian universities. On the other hand, the infocracy which Byung-Chul Han [1] writes about is being introduced into the Russian educational space. The purpose of this article is to identify ways to increase the level of conscious independence of students (schoolchildren and students) in the modern conditions of their lives.

Keywords: life, purpose of life, meaning of life, human education, human soul, human spirit.

The basic concept of this research is *the concept of human life*. Understanding life as a way to resolve the contradiction between the inner and outer worlds of human life serves as the basis for defining the goals of life. By human education, we mean the acquisition of conscious independence in the exploration of space and time of human life. And this development occurs as a result of human activity, the object of which is a person himself. Education should contribute not only to the achievement of human life goals, but also to the realization of their significance and meaning. By meaning, we understand the importance of human performance for the future.

The traditional goals of man's personal and private life are well known: at a young age, he needs to get an education, master a profession, create a family and normal living conditions. But the goals of a person's social life, which are historically specific to each state, are largely uncertain.

The common grounds for determining the goals of man's personal and social life are his natural qualities: dependence on the inner and outer worlds of life, uncertainty of attitude to the outer and inner worlds, rhythmic processes of life, procreation, the ability to transform the energy of the outer world into the energy of the inner world and vice versa. The need to realize these qualities serves as the basis for determining the goals of life. Thus, the feeling of dependence generates a desire to reduce it, and the result of the realization of this desire is the freedom a person finds. Reducing the degree of uncertainty is achieved through a person's knowledge of himself and the outside world, including knowledge of the rhythms of life. Physical and intellectual labor, and human creativity have become a way to transform the energy of the outside world into the energy of the inner world. Mental and spiritual qualities of a person that determine his emotional life refer to the properties acquired in the course of human history.

The presence of positive (ability to work, emotional and intellectual) and negative (dependence and uncertainty) qualities of a person indicates the inconsistency of his development, the resolution of which is entrusted to human education, the purpose of which is to increase the level of his conscious independence. Achieving this goal allows a person to be independent in his life, to determine the further goals of his life by himself. Thus, the goals of a person's education at the beginning of his life are the goals of his life. But the possibilities of achieving further life goals depend on the external world of a person's life, which is always historically specific.

What we have said does not contradict Michel Montaigne's definition of the purpose of life: "The goal, as I believe, is always the same for everyone, namely, to live freely and independently; but people do not always choose the right path to it" [2, p. 373].

The question of choosing the path to freedom and independence is determined primarily by the relationship between the inner world of a person's life and the outside world. The external world, which includes the forces of nature and society, is opposed by the forces of the inner world of human life. Understanding the patterns of interaction between these worlds is the basis for choosing paths to human freedom and independence.

Mythology, religion, philosophy, and science have played a leading role in determining the paths to freedom and independence in the history of mankind. Art has contributed and continues to contribute to this process, shaping the human soul and expressing the ideals of human spiritual life. (By spirit, we mean a person's desire to achieve the ideals of life, and the soul owes its birth to the harmonious integrity of feelings.)

In this regard, let us mention only one of the "Seven Wonders of the World" – the Colossus of Rhodes, erected in 294-282 BC on the Greek island of Rhodes, expressing the greatness of the spirit of the

defenders of the island from the invaders in 305-304 BC. Art can also express the uncertainty of a person's perception of the world. Thus, at the beginning of the 20th century, abstract artists (M. Chagall, K. Malevich, V. Kandinsky, and others) expressed in their works the uncertainty of human life, a characteristic feature of modern life and education in the 21st century, due to the phenomenon of infocracy.

The choice of a person's life path was influenced not only by mythology or religion itself, but by their interaction with various forms of social consciousness, for example, religion and art, mythology and philosophy, philosophy and science. It is no coincidence that Jean-Jacques Rousseau wondered about the influence of the renaissance of sciences and arts on the improvement of morals [3]. Today, Artificial Intelligence (AI) is the leader in influencing the way people are educated. The negative result of its influence is the loss of opportunities to increase the level of conscious independence of students and self-deception in assessing their achievements. Thanks to the action of AI, the external world of a person is individualized, and the social world is alienated. As a result, a person does not take part in resolving the contradictions between the public and private lives of his contemporaries.

At the beginning of the 20th century, the famous Russian writer Leo Tolstoy called for detachment from the problems of public life. In his "Address to the Russian People, to the government, Revolutionaries and the People" in 1906, he advised the following:

"In order for people to become better, it is necessary that they pay more and more attention to themselves, to their inner lives. External social activity, especially social struggle, always distracts people's attention from inner life and therefore, always inevitably corrupting people, lowers the level of public morality, as it happened everywhere and as we see it to an amazing extent now in Russia" [4, p. 390].

L. Tolstoy assessed participation in bourgeois revolutions associated with the death of people as an immoral act. He saw the improvement of the external world of people's lives in improving the work of individuals. The insufficiency of this method of improving public life seems obvious, and the history of European states, as well as Russia, speaks of disagreement with Tolstoy's understanding of public morality. The great writer underestimated the unity of the inner and outer worlds of human life, which was recognized in the books of the Old and New Testaments. The human soul painfully perceives a violation of the harmony of what is due (possible) and what is true (real) in people's lives.

The Russian writer, public figure and statesman of the end of the XVIII century A.N. Radishchev at the beginning of the story "Journey from St. Petersburg to Moscow" speaks about a change in the state of the soul,

influenced by the outside world: "I looked around me, and my soul was wounded by the sufferings of humanity" [5, p. 41]. Let's just note that people's souls vary. Therefore, the education of the soul is not an easy task, but an very important one of human education, which has not yet found proper appreciation.

Reducing the hours devoted to studying philosophy at Russian universities does not contribute to understanding the peculiarities of modern human thinking, which is characterized by students' absolute trust in information coming from various sources. Francis Bacon's teaching about idols, "which besiege people's minds" [6, p. 18], is relevant today. We have to admit that in addition to the idols of the clan, cave, square and theater, a new kind of idol has appeared – infocracy, which manifests itself in various areas of human life.

What should a person do to make his education contribute to the improvement of his life? Answering a similar question, Leo Tolstoy writes:

"The first thing is not to lie to yourself. . . .

The second is to renounce the consciousness of being right, of one's advantages, of one's peculiarities in front of other people and admit oneself guilty.

The third is to fulfill that eternal, indubitable law of man – by the labor of his whole being, without being ashamed of any labor, to fight against nature in order to maintain his own and other people's lives" [4, p. 351].

To what has been said, we add the following: both in human education and in his work, one should focus on the realization of the historical trend of increasing the degree of his conscious independence. This tendency manifests itself both in ontogenesis and in the phylogenesis of human life.

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